

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITIWDIŃ INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

TOWARD THE PROBLEM OF CHILD ADAPTATION TO SCHOOLING: A REVIEW OF RESEARCHES

Tleuzhanova Aigerim,
1st year doctoral student
Karagandy Buketov University
Aigerim_2105@mail.ru

Annotation: adaptation of first-graders is one of the most multifaceted concepts in pedagogy. Pedagogues of different epochs of society development studied this problem comprehensively. It remains topical even nowadays. The article provides information about the adaptation of children to school, about the period of adaptation child to the conditions of educational institution, to lessons, to the new routine, to procedures, to new people (teachers and classmates). Studying in the first grade - is the most responsible stage in development, since, it is here exact the foundation of morality is laid, the formation of social attitudes, attitudes to oneself, to other people, to society, beliefs are formed. The article draws certain conclusions based on the analysis of scientific literature on the issues of children's adaptation to school.

Keywords: adaptation, educational environment, junior school children, school children, psychological and pedagogical support.

One of the urgent problems of modern education is the issue of children's adaption to schooling. In recent decades, the interest of Kazakhstan's teachers and psychologists in the study of adaptation has significantly increased due to the dramatic changes in society, generating uncertainty and unpredictability. The number of maladjusted children is constantly increasing, characterized by increased anxiety, uncertainty, emotional instability, which is negatively affecting the process of perception, and subsequent the processes of upbringing and education of the child at all.

The concepts of "adaptation" and "maladaptation" are becoming more relevant in the processes of upbringing, education and labor activity. Often, by coming to school, children adapt to the new system of social conditions with uneven success, poorly adapt to new relations, requirements, mode of life activity. Introduction of new, more complex experiments, pedagogical programs, heavy workload, accelerated passage of educational material, which is characteristic of the school education system of Kazakhstan, complicate the process of adaptation of junior school children to school education. In this relationship, the study of adaptation problems, the search for optimal ways to solve them the task of pedagogical science and practice.

The term "adaptive" (from Latin "adaptare" – "приспособление") was originally used in biology (adaptation of the structure and functions of an organism to

«ÜZLİKSİZ BİLİMLENDİRİW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITİWDİN İNTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaqı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

the conditions of existence and habituation to them). In a broad sense, “adaptation” is the human adaptation to the surrounding environmental conditions. It is a constant process of active adaptation of an individual to the conditions of the social environment. Since the conditions of the social environment never remain unchanged, the process of adaptation is continuous.

According to J. Piaget, adaptation is a bilateral process, it balances “the equilibrium between the organism’s impact on the environment and the environment’s reverse impact” [7:2003], which means, it is a synthesis of processes: adaptation of behavioral schemes formed in previous stages of development to a new situation and incorporation of environmental objects into their behavioral schemes.

L.I. Bozhovich characterized the process of adaptation as “mental features and qualities that arise by adapting the child to the requirements of the environment,; Then acquire independent significance and in the order of reverse influence begin to determine the subsequent development”. [4:2010].

As part of our research, we talk about adaptation to school, about the period of the child’s adjustment to the conditions, of the educational institution, to lessons, to the routines and procedures, to new people (teachers and classmates). Each child is unique, and his adaptation process may depend on various factors, including personal characteristics, family support, and learning environment and etc.

Agreeing with L.A. Wenger’s opinion that “being ready for school does not mean being able to read, write and count. To be ready for school means to be ready to learn it all” [12:1994], we note that the process of effective, painless adaptation to school is important both for the child, for his further development, and for parents. As S. Y. Rubinstein notes in his work “On the education of habits in children”, elementary school for a child is a type of child’s activity, when for the first time he has new responsibilities. [9:1986].

The issues of adaptation of junior schoolchildren to the conditions of learning at school have been studied by many scientists, considering them from different points of view. A certain contribution to the consideration of the problem was made by the works of N.M. Aksarina [1:2007], B.N. Almazov [2:2000], S.A. Belicheva [3:1994], N.V. Vostroknutov [13:1995], A.K. Munkoev [11:2019], J.M. Grozman [5:2001], R.V. Ovcharova [6:1998], A.Yu. Potanina [8:2004] V.G. Stepatov [10:2001] and others.

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITIW DÍN INTEGRACIYASÍ»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

The conceptual bases for the development of the problem of children's adaptation in the context of school readiness in psychology is associated with the works of A.V. Petrovsky, D.B. Elkonin, Ya. Ierasek, N.I. Gutkina, R.A. Zakharov, L.M. Kovaleva, N.N. Tarasenko, L.I. Bozhovich, I.V. Dubrovina, M.M. Bezrukish and others. In the works of these authors adaptation is considered as a special moment, a phase in the formation of a person, which largely determines the nature of his further personal development.

Among Kazakhstan's scientists, the issue of children's adaptation to learning was addressed by Zhadrina M.J., Odintsova S.A., Mitrenko T.V., Rustemkhanova A.S. and others.

The study of research fields, analysis of scientific literature on the issue of children's adaptation to school allowed us to determine certain conclusions and inferences.

Firstly, adaptation in the first grade is a special and difficult period in a child's life: the child learns a new social role of a student, a new type of activity – learning, the social environment changes, there are classmates, teachers, school as a large social group in which the child is included, and finally, the child's way of life changes. A six-year-old child already has the basic prerequisites of learning: ways of cognitive activity, motivation. But, in essence, he is still a preschooler, his formation as a student occurs only in the process of teaching and the whole school life, the process of such formation under favorable conditions covers the first half of the first year of schooling.

Secondly, a child who fits into the system of school requirements, norms and social relations is called adapted. Some of the teachers include one more criterion – the child should get used to school without significant internal losses, decrease in self-esteem, mood, deterioration of well-being. This directly relates to further psychological, personal and social development. For successful adaptation to school, the child must be not only physiologically and socially developed, but also reach a certain level of intellectual and emotional-volitional development.

Third, the following should be taken into account when adapting children to school:

- social impact: in school, children are exposed to a new social environment where they must learn to interact with a variety of personalities, which can be stressful;

«ÜZLİKSİZ BİLİMLENDİRİW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITIVDIN İNTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaqı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

- level of education: the teaching load and structure of education can be a challenge for children, especially when they are exposed to new subjects and teaching methods;
- emotional well-being: children may face emotional challenges such as anxiety, fear of grades or failure, which affects their psychological well-being;
- contemporary challenges: technological advances and changes in society can create new aspects of adaptation, such as the use of digital technologies in education;
- prevention of problems: early diagnosis and resolution of adjustment problems contribute to the prevention of more serious educational and social difficulties.

Given these aspects, active attention to children's adaptation continues to be essential in the context of ensuring their full development.

Fourth, the result of failed adaptation is psychological maladaptation. It can lead to external or internal disharmonization of interaction of personality with society and himself, manifested in internal discomfort, violation of relationships and activities. It is expressed in the formation of inadequate mechanisms of adaptation of the child to school conditions. This may be conflictual relations, increased anxiety level, etc. Already in the first grade children with these problems are identified. Untimely identification of their essence, lack of specialized correctional work, entails lagging behind in the assimilation of school knowledge, decreased motivation for learning activities, various forms of deviant behavior.

Thus, the most important directions of work of a pedagogical-psychologist with primary school age children to improve the adaptive properties of personality to school education are: diagnostic work, corrective-developmental work and counseling and educational activities. At present, most teachers do not have a clear understanding of the goals and possibilities of psychological and pedagogical analysis of the adoption period, don't have the skills to implement it. A competent teacher prevents the development of maladaptation, helps to overcome adaptation difficulties, ensures faster inclusion of first-graders in learning activities, and ultimately contributes to their development.

A teacher must know the signs that characterize the tension of the adaptation process in first graders. The general list of signs can be presented in the form of the following symptoms:

- Changes of child's behavior decreasing of performance and quality of work;

«ÜZLİKSİZ BİLİMLENDİRİW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITİWDİŇ INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaqı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

•Pronounced changes in organization of activity (decreased pace, reduced time of work without distractions, appearance of difficulties in switching from one type of activity to another, etc.)

- Increased fatigue;
- Motor disinhibition or, conversely, lethargy, drowsiness;
- Decreased resistance (occurrence of frequent colds);
- Neurosis disorders (compulsive movements, fears, restless sleep, mood instability, inadequate reactions, etc.)

- Decreased body weight;
- Complaints (headache, nausea, abdominal pain, etc.)
- Violation (decrease) of the quality of educational actions (handwriting disorder, “ridiculous mistakes”, “non-use” of rules, fragmentary perception of tasks, etc.)

- Decreased learning motivation;

- Increased anxiety.

Violations of socio-psychological adaptation are noted in so-called overloaded who cannot cope with additional loads. The main reason for the violation of both physiological and psychological adaptation in these cases – is the constant effect of the stress of time limitation. “Overworked” children live in a situation of time pressure both at school and at home. They are forced to work at an unaccustomed to them very fast pace. One way or another, bad behavior – the signal of anxiety, reason to carefully observe the student and understand the causes of difficulties in adapting to school together with parents.

In recent time, there has been a tendency of experimental research of the peculiarities of the pedagogical process in connection with the emergence of school maladaptation. The peculiarities of the organization of school education, the nature of school programs and the pace of their mastering, as well as the influence of the teacher in the process of adaptation of the child in school (his emotional maturity, features of motivation, etc.) are considered. As L.V. Petrovsky noted, the decisive influence on the development of the personality of a junior schoolchild is not so much the learning activity itself, as the attitude of adults (teacher, parents) to the performance, discipline and diligence of the child, i.e. the interaction in the system “teacher – student” is the paramount moment influencing the adaptation of the child in elementary school.

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASÍDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍN INTEGRACIYASÍ»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

Taking into account functional features of the first-grader's organism, specifics of physiological and socio-psychological adaptation will allow the teacher to create optimal conditions for each student, providing successful entry into school life, effective interaction in the peer group, further personal and social development of a junior schoolchild. What attracts a child in school, when he is just preparing to go to it or has just arrived (external attributes of a new social role, new space, new subject matter), cannot hold a child's interest for a long time. The shift of interest in compliance with the requirements of the teacher and his assessments occurs in the process of mastering new skills that were not previously required of the child. After mastering them, if there is no shift of interest to the ways of acquiring knowledge, and later in the content of knowledge itself, the learning motivation begins to fade.

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«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASÍDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍN INTEGRACIYASÍ»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

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